
Cruise iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras

6th - 21st December 2022

Harbour of departure: Santos (São Paulo, Brazil)

Harbour of arrival: Niterói (Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)

Research vessel: NPqHo Vital de Oliveira

NPqHo. Vital de Oliveira – crew and iAtlantic-Petrobras Science Team

Cruise Report

21st. December 2022

1. Objectives of the Cruise

The iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras cruise aimed at describing and assessing the structure, state and functioning of deep benthic ecosystems of Santos Basin, Brazilian Meridional Margin.

These general objectives are inserted in the context of the international project iAtlantic – Integrated Assessment of Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in Space and Time (Grant Agreement no. 818123 - www.iatlantic.eu) that focus on improving scientific knowledge on factors that control distribution, stability and vulnerability of the deep and open ocean ecosystems of the Atlantic, from austral limits off Argentina to Iceland, from the eastern coasts of the USA and Brazil to western margins of Europe and Africa. The objectives also fulfil scientific studies conducted by CENPES – Petrobras, namely, Project SENSIMAR and Project of Regional Characterization (PCR) of Santos Basin.

Specific objectives of the iAtlanticBR10 – Petrobras cruise were:

- High resolution bathymetry mapping of Santos Basin shelf break and upper slope areas,
- Characterization of benthic habitats and communities through seafloor imagery and biological/geological sampling,
- Obtaining samples of cold-water corals for geochemical and taxonomic studies
- Assessing sedimentary ecosystems functioning and responses to climate-related environmental changes.

The objectives are related to the scientific tasks of iAtlantic working packages 2 (Mapping Atlantic Ecosystems), 3 (Drivers of Ecosystem Change and Tipping Points) and 4 (Impact of Multiple Stressors) in the Study Region 10 (Deep-sea continental slope, banks and cold seep ecosystems off Brazil).

2. Study Area and Regional Scientific Context

The iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras cruise explored a cross-section of the Brazilian Meridional Margin, at the southern end of Santos Basin, including sectors of the shelf break and upper slope (Figure 1). This area encompasses a dense pockmark field whose origin has been associated to salt diapirism (Mahiques et al., 2017). Previous seafloor surveys conducted by Petrobras indicated that these features coincided with reflective targets in seismic profiles, which suggested the occurrence of carbonate banks potentially associated with cold-water coral communities. Additionally, studies conducted by UNIVALI revealed that the area was targeted by commercial fishing between 2000 and 2008, with bottom trawls, gillnets and pots, aiming at profitable fish and crustacean concentrations (Perez et al., 2009). Jointly, these evidences suggested that the selected region contains unique ecosystems, with elevated diversity and productivity, whose structure and functioning patterns are little described or understood. It was also expected that these benthic ecosystems could exhibit signs of impacts produced by past bottom fishing activities.

Figure 1. Cruise iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras. Study area in the Brazilian Meridional Margin (insert at the upper right corner) and the delimited sectors A and B. Reflective targets (in black, CENPES – Petrobras) and positions of fishing trawls (in red, UNIVALI) are also shown. The green star indicates a large reflective target of particular interest.

The study region was divided into sector A, that included the shelf break and upper slope (200 – 500 m depth), and B, that included a slope “terrace” and the terrace break region (500 – 1500m depth). Geographic positions of the limits of sectors A and B are presented in Table 1. In transition zone between sectors A and B, a particular interest point is highlighted that refers to a large reflective target (Figure 1).

Table 1. Geographic positions of polygon vertices that delimit sectors B and A, explored by the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras cruise. Coordinates of a particular interest point in between the two sectors are also included. Datum WGS 1984.

	Latitude	Longitude
Sector B	-26.504543	-46.172895
	-26.702401	-46.179278
	-26.500688	-45.498764
	-26.713410	-45.498764
Sector A	-26.500688	-46.699541
	-26.713410	-46.699541
	-26.504543	-46.172895
	-26.702401	-46.179278
Interest Point	-26.563750	-46.115456

3. The Research Vessel Vital de Oliveira and the utilized sampling gear

The Research Vessel Vital de Oliveira is 78 m-long, with a beam of 20 m and a 4,200-t weight displacement. It carries a total of 90 people, including 40 berths for scientists (Figure 2).

Figure 2. NPqHO Vital de Oliveira (Brazilian Navy).

Sampling equipment available on board

- Dynamic Positioning System Kongsberg K-Pos DP-21
- Multibeam Echosounder Kongsberg EM 120 (down to 2000 m) and Kongsberg EM 122 (down to 11000 m).
- Sub-bottom Profiler Kongsberg SBP 20
- L-ADCP Teledyne WHS-300
- CTD-Rosette with 24 Niskin Bottles
- CTD SBE 9 plus (sensors: pressure, temperature, conductivity, turbidity, dissolved oxygen and chlorophyll)
- Box Corer and Van-Veen grabs

Sampling equipment not available on board

- Towed camera system (*towcam*)

The towcam system included a towed vehicle (“fish”) carrying one HD camera, two light sources and an altimeter sensor. The fish is towed by a 1,500 m-long optic fibre cable operated by a dedicated which that was installed on the ship, exclusively for this cruise (Figure 3). The fish can be operated up to 2 m above the seafloor between 250 and 1500 m depths.

Figure 3 – Towcam system operated during the cruise iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras. A, “fish”; B, which containing 1500 m-long optic fibre cable.

4. Scientific Party

The scientific party included 19 components divided into senior scientists (2), post-doctorates (3), Phd and MSc students (3), undergraduate students (10) and one technician, all involved with oceanography and marine biology research in five national institutes: University of Vale do Itajaí – UNIVALI (7), Federal University of Santa Catarina – UFSC (2), Federal University of Espírito Santo – UFES (5), Oceanographic Institute - University of São Paulo – IOUSP (4), Centre for Research and Development -CENPES, Petrobras (1) (Table 2). Halésio Barros Neto (CENPES) acted as chief scientist. Jose Angel Perez (UNIVALI) led the iAtlantic research team.

Table 2. Scientific party at cruise iAtlantic_BR10-Petrobras, Santos – Niterói, 6th – 21st December 2022.

Name	Intitution	Row	Field of work	e-mail address
Halésio Milton Correa de Barros Neto	Petrobras	Chief scientist	Biology	halesio.barros@petrobras.com.br
Jose Angel Alvarez Perez	UNIVALI	Senior Scientist	Oceanography	angel.perez@univali.br
Luis Carlos da Silva	IOUSP	Technician	Oceanography	luistec@usp.br
Camila Fernanda Silva	IOUSP	Port-Doc	Oceanography	fercamis@gmail.com
Renata Carolina Mikosz Arantes	UFSC	Port-Doc	Oceanography	arantesre@gmail.com
Rafael Schroeder	UNIVALI	Port-Doc	Oceanography	schroederichthys@gmail.com
Daniela Yepes Gaurisas	UFES	PhD St.	Biology	d.gaurisas@gmail.com
Júlia Alves Costa	UNIVALI	PhD St.	Oceanography	juliaal_costa@hotmail.com
Pedro Oliveira Nascimento	UFSC	MSc St.	Oceanography	p.oliveira413@gmail.com

Ana Lara Flores dos Santos	UFES	Undergrad. St.	Oceanography	ana.santos.02@edu.ufes.br
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Ricardo Utzig Nardi	UNIVALI	Undergrad. St.	Oceanography	ricardoutzig@hotmail.com
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5. Sampling Activities and Cruise Routine

The sampling activities conducted during cruise iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras are described in Table 4, below.

Table 4. Summary of data acquisition and sampling activities during iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras.

Activity		Description
CTD/ L-ADCP casts	CTD	Continuous measurements of temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen concentration, fluorescence, turbidity and current speed/ direction along the water column. Maximum data acquisition was 1000m. The rosette carrying CTD and L-ADCP was lowered to a minimum altitude of 80 m (above the seafloor). Some casts supported the laboratory experiments providing bottom temperatures and seawater used in sediment incubation.
Box Corer deployments	BCS	Sediment and benthic fauna sampling conducted to: (a) support on board laboratory experiments with live organisms, (b) assess environmental DNA, (c) analyse the sediment microbial community, (d) characterize substrate type (grain size and organic matter) and (e) characterize benthic infauna and epifauna. Deployments that supported laboratory experiments were conducted in 1000 and 700 m-deep areas. All other deployments were distributed in selected areas of sectors A, B.
Towcam profiles	Tcam	The towcam system was towed over the seafloor to produce continuous images of the benthic environment. Sites of the towcam profiles were defined according to the bathymetric survey and in areas where cold-water coral banks were likely to occur.

Bathymetry mapping	MBES	Bathymetric survey conducted with the multibeam echosounder with the purpose of delineating the seafloor surface morphology. The bathymetric survey was conducted along pre-determined parallel track lines.
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On board scientific activities were distributed according with an initial strategy that prioritized sediment sampling in the deepest sectors of the study area (sector B) to secure the development of experiments in the vessel's wet lab. As this task was completed, bathymetry mapping would initiate providing seafloor descriptions as required to position the first towcam profiles. However, the first box corer deployments were not effective due to main which failures (8th of December) and the towcam system became inoperable after the first video profile (9th of December). Based on these circumstances, on December 10th the original sampling strategy was then altered, now prioritizing the environmental description of the study area (10 – 13th December). That included intensification of the bathymetric survey (Table 5) and a CTD cast transect across the slope bathymetric gradient. As the which problem was solved, the box corer sampling strategy was re-designed to cover (between the 14th and the 16th of December) regions where cold-water coral communities were likely to occur. This sampling activity terminated in the deepest regions where more sediment was collected to support additional experimentation in the vessel's wet laboratory. In the morning of December 17th, the vessel resumed bathymetric sampling in order to fill in the gaps left during the previous week. On December 18th sampling operations were terminated in the study area and vessel began its route towards Niteroi harbour, Rio de Janeiro.

6. Scientific activities conducted on board

6.1. Bathymetric mapping

Bathymetric sampling was originally planned to cover three areas within sectors A and B (including the region of special interest). These were the areas of grater interest based on reflective targets distribution and concentration of fishing activity (Figure 3). Besides the general description of seafloor morphology, bathymetric mapping was essential to define the position of the towcam transects. This procedure was conducted until December 19th when the first towcam transect was carried on. As the camera system became inoperable, the bathymetric mapping strategy was altered, aiming now at the full description of sectors A and B. Complementary polygons between sectors A and B were defined and prioritized (Figure 3). After completion of these sectors, given available time at sea and favourable sea conditions, the gaps between polygons were also mapped resulting in a high-resolution seafloor map of the entire study region (Annex I – Figures I and II). The distance between track lines varied between 400 and 600 m, according with depth, maintaining a 20% overlap between the area covered by them. Along all MBES track lines a Sub-bottom profiler acquired acoustic data of the sediment layer below the seafloor line.

Table 5. Temporal distribution of activities conducted during cruise iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras. SLG, sailing.

	06/Dec tue	07/Dec wed	08/Dec thurs	09/Dec fri	10/Dec sat	11/ Dec sun	12/ Dec mon	13/ Dec tue
Sector		B	B	B	A	A	AC	AC
00:00		SLG	BC	MBES			MBES	MBES
02:00								
04:00								
06:00			MBES				CTD	CTD
08:00		Tcam	MBES	Tcam		MBES		
10:00								
12:00			CTD	CTD	MBES			
14:00				MBES			MBES	MBES
16:00	Departure		BC			CTD		
18:00		CTD		CTD				
20:00	SLG	BCS				MBES		
22:00			MBES	BCS				
00:00								
	14/ Dec wed	15/ Dec thurs	16/ Dec fri	17/ Dec sat	18/ Dec sun	19/ Dec mon	20/ Dec tue	21/ Dec wed
Sector								
00:00				CTD				
02:00	BMF							
04:00								
06:00								SLG
08:00	CTD							
10:00								
12:00		BCS	BCS	MBES	MBES		SLG	
14:00								
16:00	BCS							Port call
18:00						SLG		
20:00								
22:00								
00:00								

Figure 3. Pre-defined sectors for bathymetric mapping during iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition. Sectors A, B, and the point of interest (pi) were original priority areas. AC, were complementary areas also mapped as well as the gaps in between them.

6.2. Characterization of Benthic Habitats and Communities

Benthic habitats and communities were characterized by seafloor imaging, box corer samples (infauna, epifauna and substrate types) and CTD profiles (water column properties).

Seafloor imaging

A pilot towcam system operation was conducted in a 200 m-deep area along the route from Santos to the study area. This trial allowed the iAtlantic team and crew members to define safe routine procedures to deploy and retrieve the fish, control the fish altitude, check best settings for camera and light sources, and get familiar with the camera software and image acquisition system during the video profile.

Based on the first seafloor maps produced by MBES in the deepest regions of the study area (~850 m), the first towcam profile was planned to move on a 2 NM-long straight line over the rims of two pockmarks (Figure 4). The fish was lowered for 45 minutes with the vessel moving at approximately 1 knot until the seafloor was visible and was then kept 2 m over the seafloor, on average, for best seascape visualization (see Annex Table I). The towcam was towed for 2 hours, producing an adequate visualization of the sedimented substrate and numerous components of megafauna (Figure 4). After this period, communication with the camera system was lost and the fish was immediately retrieved to deck. The builders of the camera were contacted from the ship and guided the navy crew to conduct a system check-up. It was finally detected a irreparable rupture in the optic fibre cable. The towcam system could no longer be operated and the seafloor imaging activity was cancelled.

Characterization of substrate, infauna e epifauna

A total of 35 box corer deployments was distributed within sectors A and B and on the point of interest, covering regions of pockmark rims and ridges previously detected in the bathymetry survey (Annex – Figure II). This strategy aimed at the description of substrate types, and characterizing the diversity of epifauna (with a special interest on octocorals) and infauna (macrofauna and meiofauna) associated to the geological features. The sediment collected in the valid box corer deployments (28) were totally processed by 1000 and 300 μm sieves (Figure 5). Specimens were preserved in ethanol and sediment subsamples were frozen for posterior granulometric and organic matter content analysis. Coral rubble mostly formed by fragments of stony corals (*Madrepora*, *Solenosmilia* and *Lophelia*) were found in 24 box corer samples. In two stations, named “Coral 17” and “Coral 24” (Annex) the coral rubble dominated the substrate. These samples were collected over ridges raising in between pockmarks, suggesting that they could be coral banks (Figure 6). At station “Coral 24” a live black coral colony was captured.

Figure 4. Seafloor region of Santos Basin explored by the towcam profile (black line) (A) during the iAtlantic_BR10 – Petrobras expedition; (B) towcam control centre in the RV Vital de Oliveira dry lab; (C) seafloor image produced by the towcam system.

CTD casts

CTD casts were initially conducted in sector B, down to 1000 m depths, in order to support of the experiments with living organisms in the vessel’s wet lab. These six casts were essential to provide the experiments with information on the environmental temperatures and deep water samples to be used in the experiments. In addition, a CTD transect was conducted across the depth profile with deployments over the 300 m, 400 m, 500 m and 700 m isobaths (Annex – Table III, Figure II). This strategy intended to characterize the water mass structure influencing shelf break and slope habitats.

Figure 5. Seafloor sediment sampling with box corer during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition. A, total sediment sample collected in one box corer deployment; B, on deck sediment processing with sieves; (C) stony coral fragment; (D) live black coral colony captured in a box corer deployment.

6.3. Study on the functioning of sedimented benthic ecosystems

Experimental activities were conducted by the UFES team on board. Seafloor sediment was initially collected by 10 valid box corer deployments (Annex - Table III). Before each deployment, CTD casts recorded environmental temperature as well as deep water samples. Four box corer samples (1000 m-deep) had surface sediments (upper 10 cm-deep layer) collected with 10 cm diameter corers and taken to a freezer in wet laboratory where they were incubated in seawater at *in situ* temperature of 4°C (Figure 6). After sediment stabilization (12 hours under aeration) two types of algae were added to the cores (fresh and degraded). These algae were grown on land and were isotopically marked (^{13}C e ^{15}N). The experiments continued for 48 hours. After this period, sediment samples were collected for microbiological analysis and frozen for analysis on land. The remaining sediment was sieved through a 300 μm mesh in order to retain specimens of the macrofauna. These specimens were fixed in formalin 10%.

A second experiment was developed with sediment collected by 6 box corer deployments conducted at approximately 600 m depths. Sediment cores were incubated in seawater collected at the same depths and

maintained at 8°C, according with observations made *in situ* by CTD casts. The experiment followed the same protocol previously described but only fresh isotopically marked (¹³C e ¹⁵N) algae were added.

Additional samples of surface sediments (upper 10 cm-deep layer) were collected from the box corer sample to support studies on macrofauna and meiofauna communities, microbiology and environmental-DNA (eDNA). These samples were preserved according with specific protocols for posterior analysis on land.

Figure 6. Box corer surface sediment sampling (A) to support incubation experiments (B) conducted during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition.

7. Acquired data

Table 6 summarizes all data acquired during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition and made available among the involved institutions (UNIVALI, IOUSP, UFES, UFSC, CENPES-Petrobras e DHN – Brazilian Navy). They include 11 video clips produced during the towcam profile.

Table 6. Summary of data acquired during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition and made available among the involved institutions.

Type of data	Format	State
Sub Bottom Profile	.RAW	Raw
	.SEG	Processed
Bathymetry	.ALL	Raw
	.ASCII	Processed
	.TIF	Processed
	.RASTER	Processed
	.SHP	Raw
	.DXF	Processed
Temperature, turbidity, salinity, chlorophyll	.HEX	Raw
	.MRK	Processed
	.HDR	Processed

	.XMLCOM	Raw
Current speed profile	.OOO	Raw
	PDF de cada perfil Manual LADCP	- -
Video	.mp4	11 Clips

8. Final Remarks

- The sampling plan originally developed for the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition was severely impacted by the towcam system inoperability. The video transect obtained, however, contains unique information about the sedimentary habitats that dominate the Santos Basin slope region and their fauna.
- The contingency plan conducted throughout the expedition produced important complementary results, in particular the bathymetric map of the entire study region with a 24 m pixel resolution (originally only the areas to be explored with the towcam system were expected to be mapped). This high spatial resolution allowed for a refined interpretation of seafloor morphology, revealing unknown geological features and the identification of marks produced by fishing trawls in the past. Combined with substrate description from the extensive sediment sampling, the seafloor morphological description will allow an improved understanding on Santos Basin deep habitats and guide future studies in the area.
- The seafloor sediment sampling with box corer produced a large set of biological samples capable of supporting qualitative studies macro and meiofauna diversity in the region. Also coral fragments collected also supported previous inferences about the distribution of coral banks.
- The experiments that addressed functioning of deep sedimentary ecosystems were also impacted by technical problems on board. Nonetheless they were successfully finalized and expanded to shallower areas.

9. References

Mahiques, M.M.; Schatner, U.; Lazar, M.; Sumida, P.Y.G.; Souza, L.A.P. 2017. An extensive pockmark field on the upper Atlantic margin of southeast Brazil: spatial analysis and its relationship with salt diapirism. *Heliyon* e00257.

Perez, J.A.A.; Pezzuto, P.R.; Wahrlich, R.; Soares, A.L.S. 2009. Deep-water fisheries in Brazil: history, status and perspectives. *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.* 37(3): 513-541.

10. Anexes

Table I. Summary of towcam operations during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition

	Test	iAtlantic_BR_01
Data	07/12/2022	09/12/2022
Heading (deg)	128	55

Deployment

Hour	09:44	06:43
Depth (m)	216	786
Lat	-25.9102	-26.6955
Long	-45.984	-45.9926

Bottom

Hour	10:20	07:37
Depth (m)		
Lat	-25.912	-26.6867
Long	-45.9824	-45.9812

Retrieval

Hour	10:30	09:13
Depth (m)		
Lat	-25.9136	-26.6737
Long	-45.9814	-45.9642

On deck

Hour	10:44	10:03
Depth (m)		809
Lat	-25.916	-
Long	-45.9798	-

Table II. Summary of box corer deployments conducted during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition. Gear, sampler: BC- Box Corer, VV – Van-Veen Grab; Depth in metres; Hour in GMT – 3h; Exp., sediment incubation experiment; e-DNA, environmental DNA; microb., microbiology analysis; gran., granulometry and organic matter content analysis.

#	Station	Gear	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	Date	Hour	Validity	Exp.	e-DNA	microb.	gran.	macrofauna	meiofauna	corals
1	B-1000	BC	26.6261	45.8375	1066	07/12	21:22	no							
2	B-1000	BC	26.6261	45.8375	1064	07/12	22:14	no							
3	B-1000	BC	26.6261	45.8375	1064	07/12	23:09	yes	x	x	x	x	x	x	
4	B-1000	BC	26.6261	45.8375	1064	07/12	00:33	yes	x	x	x	x	x	x	
5	B-1000	BC	26.6261	45.8375	1064	08/12	03:10	no							
6	B-Pesca	BC	26.6124	46.0317	631	14/12	12:47	no							
7	B-Pesca	BC	26.6123	46.0317	631	14/12	13:50	yes	x	x	x	x	x	x	
8	B-Pesca	BC	26.6123	46.0317	631	14/12	14:02	yes		x	x	x	x	x	
9	coral 11	VV	26.6122	46.0545	653	14/12	16:07	no							
10	coral 11	VV	26.6122	46.0545	653	14/12	16:53	no							
11	coral 11	BC	26.6122	46.0545	653	14/12	18:24	yes		x	x	x	x	x	
12	coral 10	BC	26.6279	46.0608	646	14/12	20:09	yes		x	x	x	x	x	
13	coral 9	BC	26.6466	46.0741	655	14/12	22:10	yes		x	x	x	x	x	x
14	coral 8	BC	26.6388	46.0815	645	14/12	23:50	yes		x	x	x	x	x	x
15	coral 8	BC	26.6387	46.0815	642	15/12	00:58	yes				x	x	x	x
16	coral 7	BC	26.5600	46.1162	590	15/12	02:20	no							
17	coral 7	BC	26.5600	46.1162	590	15/12	03:26	yes				x	x	x	x
18	coral 6	BC	26.5852	46.1185	615	15/12	04:50	yes				x	x	x	x
19	coral 5	BC	26.5971	46.1395	583	15/12	06:11	yes				x	x	x	x
20	coral 4	BC	26.5296	46.3749	443	15/12	09:04	yes				x	x	x	x
21	coral 3	BC	26.6263	46.4075	444	15/12	10:54	yes				x	x	x	x
22	coral 2	BC	26.6836	46.4432	453	15/12	12:39	yes				x	x	x	x
23	coral 1	BC	26.5464	46.4669	376	15/12	14:40	yes				x	x	x	x
24	coral 12	BC	26.6189	46.1618	606	15/12	18:02	yes				x	x	x	
25	coral 13	BC	26.6871	46.0313	706	15/12	20:06	yes				x	x	x	x
26	coral 14	BC	26.6793	46.0031	734	15/12	21:30	yes				x	x	x	x
27	coral 15	BC	26.6759	45.9670	793	15/12	21:10	yes				x	x	x	x

28	coral 16	BC	26.6553	45.9804	769	15/12	00:22	yes					x	x	x	x
29	coral 17	BC	26.6283	45.9350	783	16/12	02:02	yes					x	x	x	x
30	coral 17	BC	26.6283	45.9350	779	16/12	02:55	yes					x	x	x	x
31	coral 18	BC	26.5680	45.9576	710	16/12	04:44	yes					x	x	x	x
32	coral 19	BC	26.5784	45.9071	803	16/12	06:16	yes					x	x	x	x
33	coral 20	BC	26.5617	45.9071	756	16/12	07:51	yes					x	x	x	x
34	coral 21	BC	26.5470	45.8126	998	16/12	10:05	yes					x	x	x	x
35	coral 22	BC	26.5170	45.9487	782	16/12	13:41	yes					x	x	x	x
36	coral 23	BC	26.5910	45.9025	801	16/12	15:32	yes					x	x	x	x
37	coral 24	BC	26.6141	45.9292	739	16/12	17:13	no								
38	coral 24	BC	26.6141	45.9292	739	16/12	17:55	yes					x	x	x	x
39	coral 24	BC	26.6142	45.9292	737	16/12	19:06	yes					x	x	x	x
40	coral 24	BC	26.6141	45.9292	740	16/12	20:05	no								
41	coral 25	BC	26.6302	45.9361	749	16/12	21:27	no								
42	coral 25	BC	26.6307	45.9366	750	16/12	22:00	no								
43	B-1000	BC	26.5413	45.8073	994	17/12	01:27	no								
44	B-1000	BC	26.5413	45.8073	994	17/12	02:34	no								
45	B-1000	BC	26.5413	45.8073	998	17/12	05:26	yes	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
46	B-1000	BC	26.5413	45.8073	998	17/12	06:19	yes	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table III. Summary of CTD casts conducted during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition. Depth in metres; Hour in GMT – 2h.

Cast	Date	Hour	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	CTD depth
1	7/12	20:06	26.6261	45.8375	1067	988
2	8/12	14:18	26.7022	45.9037	1016	936
3	9/12	12:08	26.6657	45.9535	816	734
4	9/12	17:18	26.5672	45.7901	1078	990
5	11/12	17:05	26.5861	46.5552	301	266
6	12/12	05:30	26.5973	46.4325	409	352
7	13/12	05:23	26.6066	46.2471	506	452
9	14/12	08:03	26.6134	46.0826	601	540
8	17/12	00:41	26.5413	45.8073	994	896

Figure I. MBES track lines of the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition

Figure II. Bathymetric map of the study area produced during the iAtlantic_BR10_Petrobras expedition. Stations with box corer deployments are indicated by red squares. Stations with CTD casts are indicated by white dots. A black line indicates the towcam transect position.

